

Challenges Created By Globalization for the HR Management

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Abstract:

This paper identifies the effect of globalization on the hr department and it's management .globalization is increasing rapidly having both negative and positive effects. This paper identifies the reasons which have led to the spread of globalization. Among them are the advancement in technology, transport, the increase of multinationals, reduction of trade barriers , global media etc. Furthermore the major challenges faced by the hr department and hr managers due to globalization have been discussed and one of the biggest challenges is managing a diverse workforce and creating a friendly environment for a healthy and successful organization. Along with this, attracting talented workers is a major focus of the hr departments now as there is a shortage of talent. Operating successfully in the global competitive market has now become difficult and complex for organizations .increasing interconnectedness and interdependence highly effects the policies and strategies of the hr department designed to achieve the goals and objectives of the organization. Importance of strategic human resource management is also discussed .human resource departments have changed to strategic human resource department to participate successfully in the global workplace. The traditional roles of an hr department have been discussed and how they have undergone changes have been outlined. Hr department is the core of organizations as it deals with the employee related issues. A well operated hr department means a smooth and successful organization.

Keywords: Globalization Challenges, HR Management

INTRODUCTION

Globalization refers to the changes in the world where we are moving away from self-contained countries and toward a more integrated world. Globalization of business is the change in a business from a company associated with a single country to one that operates in multiple countries. The impact of globalization on business can be placed into two broad categories: **market globalization** and **production globalization**.

Market globalization is the decline in barriers to selling in countries other than the home country. This change will make it easier for your company to begin selling products internationally, since lower tariffs keep consumer prices lower and fewer restrictions when crossing borders makes it easier for a company to enter a foreign market. It also means that companies must consider other cultures when developing their business strategies and potentially adjust the product and marketing messages

Production globalization is the sourcing of materials and services from other countries to gain advantage from price differences in different nations.

Globalization is not a new phenomenon. It existed from before and now has spread all over the world. It has reduced territorial boundaries and lead to time and space compression. It has extended the human relationships and activities beyond boundaries and has increased their velocity /speed. It has connected the world with each other which has increased interdependence. the events occurring in one area effects the people living in distant locations but a negative effect of globalization is that it has created winners and losers leading too new patterns of inequality Some take globalization as a positive force and some take it as a negative force.

FACTORS INCREASING GLOBALIZATION

1. Improved transport, making global travel easier. For example, there has been a rapid growth in air-travel, enabling greater movement of people and goods across the globe.
2. Improved technology has made it easier to communicate and share information around the world. E.g. internet.
3. Growth of multinational companies with a global presence in many different economies.
4. Growth of global trading blocks which have reduced national barriers. (e.g. European Union, NAFTA, ASEAN)
5. Reduced tariff barriers encouraging global trade.
6. Firms exploiting gains from economies of scale to gain increased specialization. This is an important feature of new trade theory.
7. Growth of global media.
8. Global trade cycle. Economic growth is global in nature. This means countries are increasingly interconnected. (e.g. recession in one country affects global trade and invariably causes an economic downturn in major trading partners.)
9. Financial system increasingly global in nature. When US banks suffered losses due to sub-prime mortgage crisis, it affected all major banks in other countries who had bought financial derivatives from US banks and mortgage companies.
10. Improved mobility of capital. In past few decades there has been a general reduction in capital barriers, making it easier for capital to flow between different economies. This has increased the ability for firms to receive finance. It has also increased the global interconnectedness of global financial markets.
11. Increased mobility of labour. People are more willing to move between different countries in search for work. Global trade remittances now play a large role in transfers from developed countries to developing countries.

Human resource management (HRM, or HR) is a function in organizations designed to maximize employee performance in service of their employer's strategic objectives. HR is primarily concerned with how people are managed within organizations, focusing on policies and systems. It is a strategic and comprehensive approach to manage people and the workplace culture and environment. Effective HRM enables employees to contribute effectively and productively to the overall company direction and the accomplishment of the organization's goals and objectives. HRM is moving away from traditional personnel, administration, and transactional roles, which are increasingly outsourced. HRM is now expected to add value to the strategic utilization of employees and that employee programs impact the business in measurable ways. The new role of HRM involves strategic direction and HRM metrics and measurements to demonstrate value.

Human resources manager is a key manager in an organization. He is the one who formulates human resources policies, strategies, and plans. It is he who provides direction for all the human resources activities and he ensures implementation of human resources plans, policies and strategies through the managers in various deponents and at various level. Human resources manager is also a line manager since he is directly involved in understanding, guiding and managing the operating people. If the HR manager fails, the whole operation fails. Human resources manager is not only involved in planning, recruiting or placing the people, but developing, training, motivating, actuating, redeeming by counseling, appraising, and so on.

FUNCTIONS OF TRADITIONAL HR DEPARTMENTS

1- Manpower Planning:

It involves the planning for the future and finding out how many employees will be needed in the future by the business and what type of skills should they possess. It depends on (no. of vacant jobs, growth of the business, productivity, technological changes).

2- Job analysis and Job description:

HR Department prepares Job analysis and Job description for the prospective vacancies.

A **job analysis** is the process used to collect information about the duties, responsibilities, necessary skills, outcomes, and work environment of a particular job.

Job descriptions are written statements that describe the contributions, outcomes, duties, qualifications, reporting relationship and co workers.

3- Determining wages and salaries:

HR Department is also involved in conducting market surveys and determining the wages and salaries for different position in an organization. These decisions may be taken in consultation with top management and the Finance department.

4- Recruitment and Selection:

The hr department recruits the best candidates for the vacancy. This is very important for the success of the business.

5- Performance Appraisal:

Once the employees are recruited, the HR Department has to review their performance on a regular basis through proper performance appraisals. Performance appraisal is the process of obtaining, analysing and recording information about the relative worth of an employee. The focus of the performance appraisal is measuring and improving the actual performance of the employee and also the future potential of the employee. Its aim is to measure what an employee does. On the basis of performance appraisal the HR Department will set up an action plan for each employee. If the employee needs any training then he provided that.

6- Training and development:

Hr department carries out training and development programs to improve the efficiency level of the employees.

7- Employee motivation:

Hr department is responsible for the motivation of the employees. a well-motivated workforce means more productivity and a successful organization.

8- Addressing employees' grievances:

HR department is the link between the workers and the management. Employees grievances related work environment are usually entertained and resolved by the HR Department.

9- Implementing organizational policies:

HR Department coordinates with line manager and see that the organizational policies are being implemented in a proper manner. Corrective actions are taken for those employees who do not follow the rules and regulations of the organization.

10- Dismissal and redundancy:

Hr department takes the redundancy and dismissal decisions for the betterment of the organization.

A major environmental change that has taken place in the last fifteen years is the globalization of business. The world has become a global village and business has become global in character. Organizations are venturing beyond national boundaries in the pursuit of business opportunities.

Globalization has a major impact on the management of human resources in developing countries. It has led to homogenization and convergence in organization strategies, structures and processes as well as in consumer choice. With accelerating globalization, organizations have had to change and new trends have set in even in the management of human resources. Globalization has led to changes in organization design and organization structures are leaner thus improving efficiency but having a negative impact on staff numbers which have had to be reduced. This means employees have been retrenched in many sectors like in order for those organizations to gain competitive advantage. Reward management systems have changed and even the human resource planning strategy is to have a leaner staff in the core areas and to hire part time workers in a bid to reduce costs and to enable the business to run profitably and efficiently. The non-core jobs have been outsourced which has led to an increase in independent contractors to service industries. However the homogeneity that results from globalization has had a major effect in developing countries because of brain drain. Globalization can therefore be said to have had a phenomenal impact on a developing economy is both positive and negative as explored in the paper.

With the rise of globalization, companies of all sizes are now interacting with customers and stakeholders from diverse cultures, languages and social backgrounds. In response, many human resources managers seek to hire employees from equally diverse backgrounds. Companies engaging in this diversity recruitment recognize the value of having people on staff that their customers can relate to, and they know that having a team of diverse people contributes to the range of ideas and influences within the organization.

A further effect of globalization on HR management is a push for professional development. Professional development is concerned with providing employees opportunities to achieve their career-related goals. Professional development is important to globalization because it creates a win-win situation. The employees feel as though the organization is concerned with providing a range of skills and competencies for their employees. Emphasis on the training of the employees is placed to teach them the competencies needed to compete in the global market place. But along with these positive effects there are a lot of challenges faced by the hr department due to globalization.

Human Resources departments are transforming. The new global world has widened the talent pool for excellent and marginal workers, and for permanent and fluid workers. An organization's talent can be a source for a sustained competitive advantage and can affect important organizational outcomes such as survival, profitability, customer satisfaction level, and employee performance. Human resources need to take advantage of technology and data analytics to build a global human resource information system that collects and stores data from various sources. The system will help to analyze the data to provide business insights, predict future needs and develop strategies to fill those needs. Companies with the ability to foresee and sustainably manage their workforce needs – especially for high skills – will gain the decisive competitive advantage. The global supply of talent is short of its long-term demand, and the gap is a challenge for employers everywhere. The shortage between the demand and supply of talent is likely to continue to increase, notably for highly-skilled workers and for the next generation of middle and senior leaders. Organizations need to place greater emphasis on attracting human capital rather than financial capital. Businesses need to adapt the global changes for the effectiveness of business and organizations. Only the multinationals that will be willing to adapt their human resource practices to the changing global labor market conditions will be able to attract, develop and retain the right talent, and will likely succeed in the global competition.

Another very big challenge for global organizations' human resource departments is to manage a workforce diverse in culture and language skills, and distributed in various countries. It is critical that the businesses not only familiarize with local ways of doing business, and understand the needs of local consumers, but also develop a global mindset among their employees. Being at the center of globalization, multinational

organizations need to learn to integrate diverse value systems and espouse shared global work values to create an environment, where workers are able to communicate and coordinate their activities to reach common goals. Human resources must play new roles and responsibilities in leading the organization in uncharted waters of globalization. Along with these there are many other challenges also faced by the organizations.

OTHER CHALLENGES FACED BY THE ORGANIZATIONS

- 1- With the presence and influence of more multinationals and transnationals, as well as higher standards and competitions, there is possibility for many small indigenous units to be sick
- 2- Many large and giant units will benefit from the economies of scale but the units without the merit of economies of scale will be forced to wind up.
- 3- international standardization requirements are bound to dictate higher quality specifications which make it difficult for less quality conscious business enterprises to survive in the highly competitive global market.
- 4- Large investment and modernization would require highly skilled and technically trained people who would replace less-trained, unskilled and redundant workforce.
- 5- Increasing number of industrial houses are bound to introduce schemes for golden handshake
- 6- Import of technology may become more common in the days to come resulting in increasing requirement of highly skilled manpower.
- 7- Greater and greater training needs are bound to be identified for updating the technological and behavioral skills.
- 8- There would arise greater needs for interpersonal skills, behavioral and counseling skills of executives and hence greater training needs in this direction are bound to arise.
- 9- Greater privatization of business and increase of employment in the private sector will occur which will lead to greater training needs in the private sector.
- 10- Human resources would gain greater importance by virtue of greater skills and technologic expertise, and hence human side of enterprise may gain greater importance.
- 11- There would be possibility for change in Government approach to industrial relations policies; and HRM approach may receive widespread recognition. Even legislations to regulate industrial relations in this direction can be expected.
- 12- Greater number of technically and professionally trained manpower may replace untrained or marginally trained executives, technicians and supervisory staff.
- 13- Well trained executives and enlightened workforce will expect greater growth prospects, higher remuneration, facilities to prove their skill and capability, and avenues for participation.
- 14- As a result of increase in standards, intellectual and educational levels and potentiality, higher levels of needs like self-actualization needs, esteem needs and social recognition needs may supercede primary needs like physiological needs. Hence, organizations should be able to provide ways and means for satisfying such higher needs.
- 15- Quality of work life and quality circle programs may receive greater acceptance;
- 16- Computerized information system will be increasingly used in human resources management, and hence effective appraisal system will be in use increasingly.
- 17- Enlightened management will realize more and more the need for human resources approach to deal with their people on account of emerging business environment backed by all the above factors.
- 18- more liberalization and deregulation
- 19- competition for investment
- 20- increased economic independence of nations
- 21- capital, information and technology flows are on the increase, internationalization of
- 22- enterprises and creation of mergers and alliances
- 23- Competitiveness increasingly based (not on low wages or natural resources) on

knowledge/ innovation, skills and productivity. The success of global companies is to a large extent dependent on their ability to organize (within and between organizations) across national boundaries information, money, people and other resources.

- 24- Moving production overseas to reduce costs and to facilitate sensitivity to local and regional market requirements.
- 25- Contracting out and out-sourcing. It is an important rationale of out-sourcing that it, on the one hand, enables an enterprise to concentrate on its core competencies, and on the other hand, it makes service work more productive.
- 26- Outsourcing is needed not just because of the economics involved. It is required equally because it gives opportunities, income and dignity to service work and service workers.
- 27- More part-time and temporary work (especially among women, the elderly and students)
- 28- Pushing for a more deregulated and flexible labor market
- 29- More emphasis on productivity and quality
- 30- Greater employee involvement in the design and execution of work
- 31- Shifting the focus of collective bargaining from the nation/industry level to the enterprise level.
- 32- Employers are of the view that issues relevant to the employment relationship such as work re-organization, flexible working hours and contractual arrangements, and pay for performance and skills, are increasingly workplace-related, and should therefore be addressed at the enterprise level.
- 33- Downsizing the workforce.
- 34- One important response has been the introduction of flexibility in the employment relationship to increase the capacity of enterprises to adapt rapidly to market changes. This has involved measures such as flexible working hours, part-time work, different types of employment contracts to the standard ones familiar to collective IR flexibility in functions, so that employees who are multi-skilled are not confined to the performance of only one task. They can cover up for absenteeism, and make some jobs redundant, flexible pay which involves some component of pay being dependent on performance, whether of the company, a group or the individual.
- 35- Globalization has, through technology diffusion, substantially increased the introduction of new technology. This have led to the re-organization of production systems and methods of work.
- 36- Reduction of narrow job classifications and demarcation lines between managers and workers, accompanied by skills enhancement needed to perform jobs with a broader range of tasks.
- 37- Increasing areas for worker involvement in the conception, execution and control of work.

HR managers must ensure that the human resources must be developed in accordance with the thrust of the challenges of technical, technological and leadership requirements of the contemporary world. It is an important task of the HR manager to match the people and their performance of his organization with the organizational and social objectives and goals. A human resources manager must be able to develop and establish an organizational culture of team work. Cohesiveness, organizational commitment, and mutual respect and regard so that coordination would become easier and effective. HR managers today not need to rely in a small limited market to find the right employees needed to meet the global challenge, but today they can recruit the employees from around the world. Besides that the effective data based which is being used globally today also has made HRM a simple but effective task. Thus due to globalization to some extent HRM has become more efficient and effective, but relatively a simple task. The most important factor that these organizations are made up of People, and since HRM is the set of activities which deals with the people factor present in any organization, this change has affected The Human Resources Management itself alot. Human resources manager of today must ensure that the appropriate mix of employees in terms of knowledge, skills and culture

Globalization impacts human resources at businesses and organizations of all sizes. Hiring employees needed in another country requires an understanding of laws and customs in that location. Moving employees from one country to another requires a grasp of global mobility issues. Labor costs or the availability of skilled labor in

another country may prompt human resources to look at global hiring opportunities. As many businesses expand operations into global markets, human resources may attempt to manage all details from its headquarters. Successful companies need a full range of human resources services in country markets, according to "Strategic Human Resource Management" Acquisitions, joint ventures and myriad needs in the external market require the attention of an on-site human resources professional. Companies benefit from an earlier rather than later human resources addition in the foreign market, according to the authors. Global mobility doesn't just involve the many complex tasks involved in moving an individual or family from one country to another Human resources may hire specialized vendors to assist the employee's move. Evaluating taxes, planning the movement of household goods, arranging international schools and leasing suitable, safe housing and necessary visas must occur. The former employer's contract requires a waiting period of three months prior to accepting a new job. Visa arrangements may take longer than three months. Waiting to initiate the visa process will delay the employee's start date. All of these factors must be taken into account by the human resources department.

The world has undergone a dramatic change over the last few decades, the forces of globalization; technological changes have greatly changed the business environment.

Organizations were required to respond in a strategic manner to the changes taking place in order to survive and progress. Strategic Human Resource Management (SHRM) involves a set of internally consistent policies and practices designed and implemented to ensure that a firm's human capital contribute to the achievement of its business objectives. Strategic human resources management is largely about integration and adaptation. Its concern is to ensure that:

1. Human Resources (HR) management is fully integrated with the strategy and the strategic needs of the firm.
2. HR policies cohere both across policy areas and across hierarchies. HR practices are adjusted, accepted, and used by line managers and employees as part of their everyday work. SHRM practices are macro-oriented, proactive and long term focused in nature; views human resources as assets or investments not expenses; implementation of SHRM practices bears linkage to organizational performance; and focusing on the alignment of human resources with firm strategy as a means of gaining competitive advantage. The role of people in the implementation of strategic responses has a significant bearing on the success rate.

To compete in the global market place and the modern world of rapid change, they need to be more flexible, faster-moving and faster learning than before. For that firms are implementing special global training programs, the reason for doing this is to avoid lost business due to cultural insensitivity, improving job satisfaction and retention of overseas staff and enabling a newly assigned employee to communicate with colleagues abroad. Providing training for employees not only helps them develop their skills and knowledge, but it is also motivational and a building block to organizational success.

CONCLUSION

The world has become a global space and highly competitive. To survive in this great competition the hr departments need to adapt the changes brought by globalization. The strategies need to be changed and the priority of the hr department should be to develop a global mindset the hr department should focus on the long term objectives of organizations and future oriented plans. Details about the employees should be collected by the hr departments. Regarding ethnicity, cultures, gender, nationalities etc. this will enable them to develop understanding with the employees which will help to create a friendly environment. The new techniques introduced globally should be adopted and applied by the hr department which will help the managers and professionals to predict changes and take decisions. Strategies should be made to attract highly skilled talent which contribute a lot to the success of the organization. Hr managers should adopt a broader approach. It

might also teach its employees how to use a new global software platform. This emphasis on training seeks to give the company a competitive edge in the global marketplace.

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